

A Refined Inverse Predictive Transient Model of The TREAT Facility

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents model refinements of the TREAT predictive transient model to support experiment design under transient and severe accident conditions. The model consists of several components that are integrated to provide a prediction of the control rod motion to achieve the desired power level. Initially, the model was developed to support NASA-sponsored Sirius experiments for nuclear thermal propulsion applications, and it is being applied to design an experiment with TRISO-particle fuel, which requires several updates to accommodate the core configuration changes. We present initial test results of two flattop power transients, considering fresh and depleted fuel in the experiment. The results show that the model provides a prediction of the control rod motion as expected, with significant variation in the experiment power of the fresh and depleted fuel resulting in different temperature ramps. Furthermore, the model will be validated against experimental data as it becomes available.

Keywords: Predictive Transient Model, TREAT, Shaped Transient

1. INTRODUCTION

The Transient Reactor Test Facility (TREAT) at Idaho National Laboratory (INL) was designed to test materials under transient conditions ranging from mild to severe accident conditions [1]. TREAT is a thermal test facility equipped with a large irradiation position featuring a high neutron flux level in the core center, suitable for material irradiation and testing [2]. It primarily supports transient irradiation experiments, accommodating various power shapes, including exponential power bursts and shaped power bursts for an extended period [3]. These transients are constrained only by the core energy capacity or the maximum permissible enthalpy rise, allowing for simulating accident conditions in test specimens without exceeding the operation limits of TREAT [4]. Recently, TREAT underwent core reconfiguration to provide more testing space for large experiments in the core center.

Prior to the execution of the transient experiment, modeling and simulation of the experiment are needed to determine the power level and the corresponding control rod motion over time to achieve the desired power and temperature profiles experienced by the specimen. A predictive transient model of the TREAT facility was developed initially to support the design of transient experiments in TREAT dedicated to modeling NASA-sponsored Sirius fuel experiments to evaluate nuclear materials for nuclear thermal propulsion applications [5, 6]. However, the model can be generalized to various types of experiment designs.

Recently, TREAT underwent some configurational changes allowing for larger space for experiment irradiation, which significantly increases flexibility with regard to sample geometry, materials, and operating conditions. These include the big broad use specimen transient experiment rig (Big-BUSTER) experiment tube and graphite heat sink overpower safety test (GHOST) capsule, as shown in Figure 1 [7].

In this work, we refined the TREAT predictive transient model to accommodate the latest configuration changes in the TREAT facility, aiming to reduce the efforts needed to identify facility and experimental

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Figure 1. Big-BUSTER experiment tube (left) and GHOST capsule (right) [7].

setups and conditions, thereby facilitating the design of transient experiments. The primary purpose of the TREAT predictive transient model is to determine the axial movement of the control rods needed to achieve the desired transient conditions without violating TREAT operational limits. It is not intended to entirely replace traditional confirmatory analyses, which are typically conducted as part of the experiment design and approval processes.

2. METHODS & MODELING APPROACH

The Multiphysics Object Oriented Simulation Environment (MOOSE) [8] is utilized to develop the predictive transient model, incorporating several components to perform the calculations. The model uses the point kinetics solver of the neutronics analysis tool Griffin [9], the stochastic tools module of the MOOSE framework [10], and the fuel performance code BISON [11] for experiment temperature calculations. The ultimate objective of this work is to develop a refined predictive transient model of the TREAT facility that will be able to predict control rod movements to achieve the desired time-dependent demanded power shape, as developed initially for Sirius experiments presented in Reference [5, 6]. The predictive transient model primarily supports transient irradiation experiments, accommodating various power shapes, including exponential power bursts, shaped power, and flattop transients.

The TREAT initial and refined predictive transient models incorporate multiple constituent models to provide accurate predictions of reactor power, core temperature, total deposited energy, axial control rod movement, and experiment power. A schematic diagram illustrating the TREAT predictive transient model calculation workflow and the coupling scheme of the sub-models is provided in Figure 2. The model includes four primary components: (1) High-fidelity data generation model, (2) Component surrogate model, (3) TREAT transient model, and (4) Experiment thermal model.

2.1. High-Fidelity Model

The high-fidelity model of TREAT [12] utilized in this work for training data generation was originally developed using the Serpent Monte Carlo code [13]. We updated the TREAT Serpent model with the latest changes in the core configuration, which can be summarized by the redistribution of the fuel

Figure 2. Refined TREAT predictive transient model workflow with the main components.

assembly and improvements to the experiment tube and capsule designs in the central irradiation location, implemented to facilitate a broader range of transient experiments.

Figure 3 shows a radial view of two configurations of the TREAT core: the fully slotted core used in the Sirius experiments analysis and the updated configuration with the latest changes, including the Big-BUSTER setup. This model is utilized to generate datasets from steady-state calculations to train and develop surrogate models considering different control rod positions, fuel temperature, and experimental setup. These datasets include core reactivity changes, differential rod worth coefficients, and experiment power coupling factors.

In the central fuel location, a simplified geometry of a TRISO particle fuel sample is considered for the purpose of testing. This geometry is utilized from previous work that uses the TREAT predictive transient model dedicated to designing and testing TRISO particle fuel in TREAT, as detailed in Reference [14, 15].

(a) Fully Slotted Core

(b) Big-BUSTER Core

Figure 3. TREAT serpent model with experiment loaded at the center of the core.

2.2. Surrogate Models

The developed surrogate models were primarily designed to predict core reactivity and differential worth coefficients as a function of the fuel average temperature, transient control rods (C/T) position, and safety control rods (C/S) position. These models are essential for the TREAT predictive transient model to accurately predict the core total reactivity and the necessary axial control rod position to achieve this reactivity. The datasets for predicting the system's eigenvalue, generated with Serpent to build the surrogate reactivity model based on the control rod positions and fuel average temperatures, are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Generated eigenvalue data points of TREAT using Serpent at various control rod positions and temperatures.

Additionally, to allow for more flexibility in calculating the specimen power, a surrogate model was added to predict the experiment power coupling factor as a function of the average fuel temperature, transient control rods (C/T) position, safety control rods (C/S) position, and experiment fuel burnup, as shown in Figure 5. These power coupling factors are generated using the Serpent model of TREAT and the fresh and depleted TRISO-fuel specimen by relating the fission reaction rate in the specimen to the fission reaction rate in the reactor core. These surrogate models were generated using a polynomial regression model of the 4th order, utilizing the stochastic tools module in MOOSE.

3. PREDICTED RESULTS

The TREAT transient model was further refined to incorporate the developed surrogate models of the updated core configuration for reactivity, control rod worth differential coefficients, burnup-dependent power coupling factors, and an impeded inverse kinetics model for reactivity calculations. The TREAT transient model relies on five pillars: (1) Impeded inverse kinetics model: Converts the demand power signal into a reactivity demand signal using given kinetics parameters, (2) Proportional controller: Determines the equivalent reactivity of the control rod axial movement in response to the calculated demand reactivity signal, (3) Adiabatic thermal feedback model: Computes the average reactor temperature given the heat deposited in the system, (4) Point kinetics model: Computes the total power and concentrations of delayed neutron precursors based on the predicted reactivity introduced into the system, and (5) Surrogate models: Predict the reactivity introduced into the system for the point kinetics model, control rod differential worth coefficients for the control rod position controller, and coupling

Figure 5. Specimen power coupling factors for fresh and depleted TRISO fuels.

factors for the specimen power calculation. Given the predicted reactor power and the specimen power coupling factors, the deposited power within the specimen can be calculated.

The refined predictive transient model of TREAT was tested with two flattop transients with demand powers of 26.55 MW and 15.0 MW. Each transient was assumed to run until the 2.5 GJ energy safety limit of TREAT has been reached. Figure 6 shows the demand and calculated power with the predicted control rod movement to achieve the demand power level during the transient. It also shows the estimated total deposited energy and the fuel average temperature for both test cases. The predicted reactor power was consistent with the demand power, with small variations during and after the power ramp to achieve the flat power distribution. Additionally, a reasonable control rod movement can be observed within the operation range, with monotonic withdrawal of the control rods to compensate for the negative temperature feedback of the fuel.

For both transient tests, we considered the fresh and depleted TRISO-particle fuel and predicted the power coupling factors and experiment power during the transient, as shown in Figure 3. The coupling factors vary similarly for both fresh and depleted fuel, with a significant difference in magnitude, ranging from 13-14 W/MW for fresh fuel and 5-6 W/MW for depleted fuel. The power coupling factors increase as the control rod is withdrawn from the core and with the increase of the fuel average temperature. Despite maintaining the core power at a constant level, the experiment power shows a slight increase after the power ramp due to the increase in the power coupling factors.

4. SUMMARY

This paper summarizes the refinements made to the TREAT predictive transient model to accommodate the latest core configuration changes. Initially, the model was developed for the fully slotted TREAT core, considering Sirius-NTP experiments. More recently, the model was deployed for designing an experiment for TRISO-particle fuel testing in TREAT. The test results show the capability of predicting the control rod motion during transients to achieve the desired power level, determined by the temper-

(a) Power and control rod motion

(b) Core deposited energy and fuel average temperature

Figure 6. TREAT serpent model with experiment loaded at the center of the core.

ature ramp rate required to be achieved within the experiment. Future work will focus on validating the refined TREAT predictive transient model with experimental TREAT data for shaped transients to calibrate the model if needed and further increase the confidence level in the model.

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(a) Fresh TRISO-fuel

(b) Depleted TRISO-fuel

Figure 7. TREAT serpent model with experiment loaded at the center of the core.

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